

REPROHEALTH AND GENDER

RAM REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS

In this specimen, the testicle has been sectioned to see the internal parenchyma, the tissue where spermatozoa and androgen hormones (testosterone) are produced. Testicle has an outer fibrous albuginea where terminal branches of the testicular artery penetrate the parenchyma. Testicle is broadly attached to the epididymis. This organ transitionally receives (head), transports (body) and stores (tail) the sperm cells. The tail of the epididymis is continued with the deferent duct and is attached to the testicle with the proper ligament of the testis. The deferent duct is part of the spermatic chord, which also includes the testicular artery and vein. While the artery is highly convoluted the vein surrounds the artery in the so-called pampiniform plexus. In the picture below the artery was filled with red resin. All previous organs are surrounded by the testicular sheaths, which include the cremaster muscle. The tail of the epididymis is attached to the inner testicular sheath (tunica vaginalis) with the ligament of the tail of the epididymis.

1. Testicular tunica.
2. Testicular parenchyma.
3. Testicular albuginea.
4. Head of epididymis.
5. Body of epididymis.
6. Tail of epididymis.
7. Ductus deferens (vas deferens).
8. Pampiniform plexus.
9. Spermatic cord.
10. Proper ligament of testis.
11. Cremaster muscle.

SHEEP REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS

This specimen includes all the organs of the female reproductive tract. Right and left ovaries, right and left oviducts (uterine tubes), uterus, vagina, and external genitalia. Also, the urinary bladder and urethra can be identified. Ovaries are oval-shaped and approximately 2 cm long. They are attached to the uterus by the proper ligament of the ovary and to the abdominal cavity by the suspensory ligament of the ovary. Ovaries are closely related with the infundibulum of the oviduct. This part receives the oocytes and follicular liquid during ovulation. Oviduct transitionally stores and transports the oocytes towards the uterus, via the ampulla and a terminal isthmus. Fertilization of oocytes should occur in the oviduct. The uterus is the organ responsible for keeping the pregnancy. It has three main portions: two uterine horns, a body, and neck (cervix). In primates the uterus has not uterine horns. The vagina receives the penis during copulation. It is opened to the external genitalia via a short vaginal vestibule, the place where the external opening of the urethra is located (urinary tract). External genitalia include the vulva and clitoris.

1. Right ovary.
2. Left ovary.
3. Left infundibulum (oviduct).
4. Right isthmus (oviduct).
5. Right uterine horn.
6. Left uterine horn.
7. Body of uterus.
8. Cervix of uterus.
9. Vagina.
10. Rectum.
11. Mesovarium (suspensory ligament).
12. Mesometrium.
13. Intercornual ligament.

TRANSPARENT SECTION OF SHEEP OVARY

This magnified transparent section shows the two main portions of the ovary, the external cortex and the internal medulla. The cortex is the place where ovarian follicles are developing. Follicles of different sizes can be observed: secondary and Graffian. Graffian follicles are characterized by the presence of an inner cavity (antrum) filled with follicular liquid. Follicles are also responsible for producing important hormones such as estrogens and progesterone.

The ovarian medulla is the area where the vasculature of the organ is located. From here, capillaries are broadly distributed throughout the whole cortex.

1. Cortex.
2. Medulla.
3. Primordial follicles.
4. Secondary follicles.
5. Tertiary follicles.
6. Antral follicle (antrum).

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